

KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR

Latipova Shahnoza Salim qizi

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti

“Umumtexnik fanlar” kafedrası o‘qituvchisi

slatipova543@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA

Kasr tartibli tenglamalarning fizik, texnik va biologik jaroyonlarga tadbiqi katta bo‘lgani uchun butun dunyo olimlari tomonidan kasr tartibli tenglamalarni o‘rganishga bo‘lgan qiziqish ortib bormoqda. Bugungi kunda kasr tartibli aralash tipdagi tenglamalar uchun to‘g‘ri va teskari masalalarni o‘rganish va yechish dolzarb masalaga aylandi.

***Kalit so‘zlar:** Kasr tartibli hosila, Riemann-Liouville, Koshiy masalasi, Volterra integral, Mittag-Leffler funksiyasi.*

Riemann-Liouville ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar uchun Koshi tipidagi masalalar.

Ushbu kichik bo‘limda biz chiziqli kasr tartibli differensial tenglamaning aniq echimlarini tuzamiz. Riman-Liouvil kasr tartibli hosilasi

$$D^{\alpha} f = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right)^n \int_0^x \frac{f(t)}{(x-t)^{\alpha-n+1}} dt.$$

Bilan aniqlanga quyidagi boshlang‘ich shartli Koshi masalasini qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned} (D^{\alpha} y)(x) - \lambda y(x) &= f(x), (a < x \leq b, \alpha > 0, \lambda \in R) \\ (D^{\alpha-k} y)(a+) &= b_k, (b_k \in R, k = 1, 2, \dots, n = -[-\alpha]) \end{aligned} \quad (1),(2)$$

Faraz qilaylik, $f(x) \in C_\gamma[a, b]$, $(0 \leq \gamma < 1)$ bo'lsin. U holda, $C_{n-\alpha}[a, b]$ fazoda (1),(2) koshi masalasi quyidagi

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{b_j}{\Gamma(\alpha - j + 1)} (x - a)^{\alpha - j} + \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{y(t)}{(x - t)^{1-\alpha}} dt + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{f(t)}{(x - t)^{1-\alpha}} dt \quad (3)$$

Volterra integral tenglamasiga ekvivalent tenglama bo'ladi.

Biz bu tenglamani ketma ket yaqinlashish metodi orqali yechimini topamiz.

Bu metodga ko'ra,

$$y_0(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{b_j}{\Gamma(\alpha - j + 1)} (x - a)^{\alpha - j} \quad (4), (5)$$

$$y_m(x) = y_0(x) + \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{y_{m-1}(t)}{(x - t)^{1-\alpha}} dt + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{f(t)}{(x - t)^{1-\alpha}} dt$$

Bu yaqinlashishlarni operator ko'rinishida quyidagicha yozib olishimiz mumkin:

$$y_0(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{b_j}{\Gamma(\alpha - j + 1)} (x - a)^{\alpha - j} \quad (4), (6)$$

$$y_m(x) = y_0(x) + \lambda (I^\alpha y_{m-1})(x) + (I^\alpha f)(x)$$

Yuqoridagi formula orqali y_1 ni hisoblab olamiz,

$$\begin{aligned} y_1(x) &= y_0(x) + \lambda (I^\alpha y_0)(x) + (I^\alpha f)(x) = \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{b_j}{\Gamma(\alpha - j + 1)} (x - a)^{\alpha - j} + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{b_j}{\Gamma(2\alpha - j + 1)} (x - a)^{2\alpha - j} + (I^\alpha f)(x) = \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n b_j \sum_{k=1}^2 \frac{\lambda^{k-1} (x - a)^{\alpha k - j}}{\Gamma(\alpha k - j + 1)} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x - t)^{\alpha - 1} f(t) dt. \end{aligned}$$

Yuqoridagiga o'xshash y_2 uchun ham quyidagi formulani yozib olamiz:

$$y_2(x) = y_0(x) + \lambda(I^\alpha y_1)(x) + (I^\alpha f)(x)$$

Bundan,

$$y_2(x) = y_0(x) + \lambda(I^\alpha y_1)(x) + (I^\alpha f)(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{b_j}{\Gamma(\alpha - j + 1)} (x - a)^{\alpha - j} + \\ + \sum_{j=1}^n b_j \sum_{k=1}^2 \frac{\lambda^{k-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha k - j + 1)} (I^\alpha (t - a)^{\alpha k - j})(x) + (I^\alpha f)(x) + (I^\alpha I^\alpha f)(x)$$

Buni quyidagicha ixchamlab yozish mumkin:

$$y_2 = \sum_{j=1}^n b_j \sum_{k=1}^3 \frac{\lambda^{k-1} (x - a)^{\alpha k - j}}{\Gamma(\alpha k - j + 1)} + \int_a^x \left[\sum_{k=1}^2 \frac{\lambda^{k-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha k)} (x - t)^{\alpha k - 1} \right] f(t) dt \quad (7)$$

Jarayonni davom ettirib quyidagi ketma-ketlikni hosil qilamiz:

$$y_m = \sum_{j=1}^n b_j \sum_{k=1}^{m+1} \frac{\lambda^{k-1} (x - a)^{\alpha k - j}}{\Gamma(\alpha k - j + 1)} + \int_a^x \left[\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{\lambda^{k-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha k)} (x - t)^{\alpha k - 1} \right] f(t) dt \quad (8)$$

Bu ketma-ketlikda m ni cheksizga intiltirib limitga o'tsak (3) integral tenglamaning yechimiga kelamiz.

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n b_j \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{k-1} (x - a)^{\alpha k - j}}{\Gamma(\alpha k - j + 1)} + \int_a^x \left[\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{k-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha k)} (x - t)^{\alpha k - 1} \right] f(t) dt \quad (9)$$

Endi bu yechimni ko'rinishini ixchamlash uchun 1-bobda keltirib o'tilgan

$$E_{\alpha, \beta}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)} \quad \text{Mittag-Leffler funksiyasidan foydalanamiz.}$$

Kerakli o'rinlarda bu funksiya ifodasini almashtirsak quyidagi ko'rinishdagi yechimga ega bo'lamiz:

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n b_j (x - a)^{\alpha - j} E_{\alpha, \alpha - j + 1} \left[\lambda (x - a)^\alpha \right] + \int_a^x (x - t)^{\alpha - 1} E_{\alpha, \alpha} \left[\lambda (x - a)^\alpha \right] f(t) dt \quad (10)$$

Bu funksiya (3) Volterra integral tenglamasining yechimi bo'ladi va demak (1),(2)

Koshi masalasining ham yechimini ifodalaydi

Agar Koshi masalasida $0 < \alpha < 1, \lambda \in R$ bo'lsa,

$$(D^\alpha y)(x) - \lambda y(x) = f(x)$$

$$(D^{\alpha-1} y)(a+) = b$$

yechim quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$y(x) = b(x-a)^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha}[\lambda(x-a)^\alpha] + \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}[\lambda(x-a)^\alpha] f(t) dt.$$

Agar ozod had nolga teng bo'lsa,

$$(D^\alpha y)(x) - \lambda y(x) = 0$$

$$(D^{\alpha-1} y)(a+) = b$$

Quyidagicha soda ko'rinishdagi yechim olinadi:

$$y(x) = b(x-a)^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha}[\lambda(x-a)^\alpha].$$

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YHATI.

1. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 66-76.
2. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
3. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(10), 13-23.
4. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).

5. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. *World of Scientific news in Science*, 1(2), 163-176.
6. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In " *Conference on Universal Science Research 2023*" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
7. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(12), 216-220.
8. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG–LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 238-244.
9. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. *SCHOLAR*, 1(31), 263-269.
10. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 360-365.
11. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 137-141.
12. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 135–138.
13. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. *International journal of sciearchers*, 2(2), 101-103.
14. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 245-248.
15. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 102–110.

16. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
17. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(27), 106-113.
18. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(13), 115-121.
19. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 2(12), 50-56.
20. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 420–424.
21. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 425–429.
22. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO ‘LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 162-167.
23. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO ‘LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 162-167.
24. Jurakulov, S. (2023). IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(21), 143-150.
25. Jurakulov, S. (2023). CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(13), 77-87.
26. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). СОЗДАНИЕ ПРОГРАММЫ ДЛЯ ИМИТАЦИИ ШИФРОВАНИЯ МАШИНЫ ENIGMA НА ЯЗЫКЕ PYTHON. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 317-323.

27. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). STUDY THE PSYCHOLOGY OF PROGRAMMERS. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 563-568.

28. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. *Theory and practice of contemporary science*, 3(45), 305-308.

29. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (3 (45)), 305-308.

30. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 296-304.

31. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599)*, 1(10), 108-117.

32. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 288-293.

33. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 368-372.

34. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 201-205.

35. Sharopova, M. M. qizi . (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB' EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 111–119.

36. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). RSA VA EL-GAMAL OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON RAQMLI IMZOLARI. *RSA*

- OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDAGI ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZO. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 316-319
37. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA ULARNI QO'LLASH USUL VA VOSITALARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 481-486.
38. Murodov, O. T. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 130–139.
39. Jurakulov, S. Z. (2023). Nuclear energy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 514-518.
40. Oghly, J. S. Z. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYMER COMPOSITES. *American Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(10), 25-33.
41. Oghly, J. S. Z. (2023). THE RELATIONSHIP OF PHYSICS AND ART IN ARISTOTLE'S SYSTEM. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 3(11), 67-73.
42. Oghly, J. S. Z. (2023). A Japanese approach to in-service training and professional development of science and physics teachers in Japan. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 167-173.
43. Oghly, J. S. Z. (2023). BASIC PHILOSOPHICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL IDEAS IN THE EVOLUTION OF PHYSICAL SCIENCES. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 41, 233-241.
44. Oghly, J. S. Z. (2023). New Computer-Assisted Approaches to Teaching Physics. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 173-177.
45. Oghly, J. S. Z. (2023). A Current Perspective on the Relationship between Economics and Physics. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 154-159.
46. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, K. (2023). STUDYING PHYSICS USING A COMPUTER. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 148-151.

47. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 280-287.

48. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.

49. Boboqulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 223-228.

50. Quvvatov Behruz Ulug‘bek o‘g‘li. (2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. *International journal of scientific researchers*, 2(2).

51. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(11).